

L-Trail: Estimating macroscopic transition directions in scRNA-seq data via outlier-robust L-moments

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Abstract

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) provides static snapshots of cellular states, requiring trajectory inference methods to reconstruct dynamic developmental pathways. While RNA velocity models are widely used, they rely on splicing kinetics, necessitating intronic reads and limiting their applicability. Alternatively, the geometric structure of data manifolds offers insights into cellular transitions, as differentiating populations naturally form asymmetric distributions, or "comet tails," along developmental axes. However, conventional statistical skewness is susceptible to the sparsity and extreme outliers inherent in scRNA-seq data. Here, we present L-Trail, a statistical toolkit that estimates the macroscopic transition trends of actively transitioning cell clusters by evaluating geometric asymmetry using robust L-moments. Independent of splicing kinetics, L-Trail extracts directional trajectories from static expression states as a structural proxy for developmental progression and incorporates a high-dimensional permutation test to suppress artifactual outputs in sparse or symmetric populations. Across multiple diverse datasets, L-Trail demonstrated macroscopic concordance with RNA velocity in progressing clusters. Notably, in the continuous branching manifold of the Bone Marrow dataset, L-Trail inferred forward progression where standard kinetic models predicted reversed flows. Furthermore, application to a splicing-free dataset confirmed its utility in the absence of intronic data, emphasizing the importance of geometry-preserving variance transformations. Overall, L-Trail provides a transparent, geometry-dependent, and splicing-independent complementary approach for trajectory inference in single-cell transcriptomics.

1 Introduction

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) captures static snapshots of cellular heterogeneity[1]. To understand dynamic biological processes such as differentiation and development, trajectory inference methods were developed to reconstruct continuous developmental pathways from these static states using diverse strategies. For example, RNA velocity models estimate future states via splicing kinetics[2, 3]. Because this approach requires intronic reads, it increases sequencing costs and limits application to datasets where intronic information is preserved. Topological methods reconstruct continuous manifolds but require the specification of predefined root states[4, 5]. Methods evaluating developmental potential, such as CytoTRACE [6], rely on specific biological assumptions, including the correlation between transcriptional diversity and differentiation stages. Recently, deep learning-based models, such as veloVI [7], have been increasingly applied to infer cellular dynamics. While capable of capturing complex non-linear relationships, these models incur high computational costs and often lack algorithmic transparency. This opacity obscures the biological rationale behind the inferred trajectories, complicating downstream mechanistic interpretations.

As an alternative to kinetic modeling, the geometric structure of the data manifold provides information regarding cellular transitions. Differentiating populations form asymmetric distributions—a

"comet tail" effect—along the developmental axis in high-dimensional spaces. While statistical skewness can theoretically capture this directionality, conventional Product-moments (e.g., Pearson’s skewness) are susceptible to the extreme outliers, sparsity, and technical noise inherent in scRNA-seq data[8].

Here, we present L-Trail, a statistical toolkit designed to estimate the macroscopic transition trends of actively transitioning cell clusters. L-Trail captures the geometric asymmetry of cellular distributions in high-dimensional spaces using L-moments[9]. Constructed from linear combinations of Probability Weighted Moments (PWM)[10], L-moments evaluate this asymmetry while providing a framework resistant to extreme values. This approach extracts directional trends from static expression states, independent of splicing kinetics. L-Trail incorporates a high-dimensional random sign-flipping permutation test[11]. Rather than computing vectors from symmetric or sparse data, this mechanism suppresses output, preventing the generation of artifactual trajectories.

We evaluated L-Trail across multiple scRNA-seq datasets. In the Pancreas dataset, local cosine similarity analysis confirmed a structural correspondence between the macroscopic geometry captured by L-Trail and the splicing kinetics inferred by RNA velocity in specific cellular populations. In the Bone Marrow dataset—a continuous branching manifold where standard kinetic models infer reversed flows—L-Trail estimated trajectories that progress from the progenitor pool toward the terminal differentiation branches. Furthermore, application to the splicing-free Paul15 dataset demonstrated its utility in the absence of intronic data, highlighting the role of geometry-preserving data transformations. L-Trail provides a geometry-dependent, splicing-independent complementary approach for transition estimation in single-cell analyses.

2 Results

2.1 Overview of L-Trail

To infer the macroscopic transition trends of cell clusters without relying on splicing kinetics, we developed L-Trail. The algorithm evaluates the geometric asymmetry of cellular distributions within a representation space using L-moments. As conceptually illustrated along a one-dimensional axis (Figure 1A), cell populations in a progressing transitional state form an asymmetric distribution within a continuous manifold. In this configuration, a dense head of advanced cells accumulates toward the endpoint of the transition, leaving a sparse, trailing tail of delayed cells. Because statistical skewness mathematically points toward the sparse tail, L-Trail calculates the negative L-skewness vector ($-I_3$) to align the directional estimation with the forward trajectory.

Single-cell datasets contain inherent sparsity and extreme outliers, which affect conventional statistical moments. To evaluate the geometric stability of L-Trail, we compared the L-moment-based estimation against a baseline vector based on Pearson’s second coefficient of skewness (v_{Pearson}) using a simulated 1D cell distribution with introduced outliers (Figure 1B). While the conventional moment-based vector was influenced by the extreme values, the L-skewness vector ($-I_3$) maintained structural fidelity to the primary data distribution. Using order statistics, L-Trail extracts directional trends while mitigating the impact of technical noise.

Furthermore, L-Trail incorporates a high-dimensional random sign-flipping permutation test. This mechanism requires the observed directional vector to exceed a high-dimensional noise floor to achieve statistical significance. Consequently, the algorithm suppresses outputs in symmetric or sparse clusters, preventing the generation of artifactual trajectories. Additionally, during visualization, projected vectors with a norm of less than 0.01 are excluded as noise.

2.2 Pancreas dataset

We performed a spatial comparison between L-Trail and RNA velocity (scVelo) using the Pancreas dataset. As a premise of this comparison, scVelo calculates microscopic dynamics in the

high-dimensional gene expression space using splicing information. In contrast, L-Trail calculates the geometric asymmetry of cell populations within a noise-reduced principal component analysis (PCA) space (default: top 30 principal components). Although the underlying information sources for these calculations differ, we evaluated the estimated vectors by projecting both onto a shared low-dimensional PCA space.

Upon visual evaluation, the L-Trail transition vectors in transitioning clusters exhibited a macroscopic directionality similar to the vector field of scVelo (stochastic mode) (Figure 2A). However, the L-Trail vector magnitude in the Ductal cluster was small, and a vector pointing in the opposite direction to scVelo was calculated for the Ngn3 low EP cluster. Cell numbers were sufficient across all analyzed clusters, including Ductal ($n = 916$) and Ngn3 low EP ($n = 262$), indicating that these estimated vectors are not artifacts of random noise from small sample sizes (Figure 2B).

To quantitatively evaluate the directional concordance between the two methods, we calculated the cosine similarity between the mean scVelo vector and the L-Trail vector within the local neighborhoods ($k = 50$) of 1,000 randomly selected anchor cells (Figure 2C, 2D). The overall median cosine similarity was low, reaching a maximum of ≈ 0.25 . Examining the distribution by cluster, higher positive similarities were observed in clusters such as Alpha, Beta, and Delta. Conversely, transitioning clusters, including Ngn3 high EP and Pre-endocrine, which demonstrated visual directional alignment with scVelo, retained lower similarity scores.

2.3 Bone marrow dataset

To evaluate the methods on a continuous manifold where splicing-based kinetic models face challenges, we analyzed the Bone Marrow dataset. Visually, scVelo exhibited backward flows along the Erythroid (Ery) and Monocytic (Mono) lineages[12]. In contrast, L-Trail did not show reversed trajectories and estimated directional vectors pointing outward along the developmental branches (Figure 3A). A single directional vector was inferred for the root Hematopoietic Stem Cell (HSC) cluster. With the exception of the Megakaryocyte (Mega) cluster ($n = 60$), Given the sample sizes of these clusters (e.g., $n = 916$), the estimated vectors, indicating that the estimated macroscopic trends are not artifacts of random sampling noise(Figure 3B). Quantitative evaluation via local cosine similarity revealed that, with the exception of the CLP and HSC1 clusters, the median scores were centered around zero or negative across the majority of populations(Figure 3C). This included clusters where the macroscopic trajectories of L-Trail and scVelo appeared visually concordant on the 2D visualization.

2.4 Paul15 dataset

To evaluate the application of L-Trail to datasets lacking splicing information, we analyzed the Paul15 dataset. For benchmarking, we calculated Diffusion Pseudotime (DPT) using Scanpy, setting the 7MEP cluster as the root state. To evaluate the impact of variance-stabilizing transformations on L-Trail's estimation, we compared vectors computed from data preprocessed with a standard log1p transformation versus a square-root (sqrt) transformation. Visually, the DPT analysis indicated a V-shaped bifurcating developmental trajectory. While L-Trail captured the outward trends toward the terminal states, backward flows were observed in several non-terminal clusters(Figure 4A). Clusters 1, 8, 9, 11, 12, 17, 18, and 19 contained fewer than 100 cells(Supplementary Fig. S3C). Comparing the preprocessing methods, the sqrt transformation resulted in fewer reversed vectors and yielded macroscopic trajectories visually concordant with the DPT developmental gradient than the log1p transformation (Figure 4B)[13].

2.5 Dentate Gyrus dataset

Finally, to evaluate L-Trail on a dataset characterized by variable cluster sizes, discrete transitions, and multi-directional branching, we analyzed the Dentate Gyrus dataset. Visually, in clusters undergoing unidirectional transitions (such as Astrocytes, Microglia, and Granule mature), the L-Trail vectors exhibited directional trends concordant with the scVelo vector field (Figure 5A). However, transition vectors were absent for the root progenitor population (Radial Glia-like). Vectors were also absent in clusters with small sample sizes, including OL ($n = 50$), Cck-Tox ($n = 27$), and nIPC ($n = 19$) (Figure 5B). Furthermore, a backward flow was observed in the Neuroblast cluster, despite it containing $n = 417$ cells. Reflecting these geometric estimations across the manifold, the quantitative local cosine similarity scores exhibited variance and low concordance across the majority of the clusters (Figure 5C).

3 Discussion

3.1 Summary of the Core Contribution

In this study, we introduced L-Trail, a statistical toolkit to estimate the macroscopic transition trends of cell clusters in scRNA-seq data. While recent advancements in trajectory inference focus on kinetic modeling using splicing dynamics, these approaches are often limited by the requirement for intronic reads, predefined root states, or complex algorithmic assumptions[14]. By evaluating the geometric asymmetry (the "comet tail" effect) of cellular distributions using L-moments—a statistical framework resistant to outliers in single-cell data—L-Trail provides a splicing-independent, geometry-based alternative. This approach extracts macroscopic geometric trajectories from static expression snapshots, offering a structural proxy for developmental progression rather than estimating kinetic velocities.

3.2 Spatial Relationship between Kinetics and Geometry

Our comparative analysis on the Pancreas dataset indicated that the geometric asymmetry captured by L-Trail aligns with the microscopic splicing kinetics inferred by RNA velocity in transitioning populations. The quantitative evaluation yielded maximum median cosine similarities of ≈ 0.25 . This magnitude can be attributed to comparing smoothed, cluster-level aggregate vectors against microscopic, single-cell kinetic vectors. The macroscopic directional alignment suggests that, in linear and continuous developmental trajectories, the shape of the data manifold reflects the biological transition.

3.3 Advantages in Splicing-Free Data and the Mechanics of Geometric Discrepancy

The advantages of a geometry-based approach can be observed in datasets where splicing-based kinetic models face challenges. In the Bone Marrow dataset—where inferring directionality solely from splicing kinetics is difficult—L-Trail captured outward geometric trajectories. The quantitative comparison highlighted a discrepancy between visual alignment in 2D and high-dimensional quantitative similarity. We hypothesize that this discrepancy arises from the mechanics of the local k -NN clustering used for the evaluation. First, defining local neighborhoods reduces the effective sample size. Second, partitioning a continuous "comet tail" into smaller segments fragments the macroscopic asymmetry. Consequently, micro-clusters formed within the tail region suffer from sparsity and high variance, which can degrade the precision of L-moment estimation and lower the cosine similarity score.

Application to the splicing-free Paul15 dataset demonstrated the impact of variance-stabilizing transformations. Because L-Trail relies on geometric asymmetry extending into high-expression

ranges, the standard \log_{1p} transformation compresses this distributional shape[13]. Using a square-root (sqrt) transformation preserved the macroscopic "comet tail," reducing backward flows and highlighting the role of geometry-preserving preprocessing.

3.4 Clustering Dependence and the Resolution Trade-off

L-Trail possesses mathematical limitations derived from its cluster-based design. Because the algorithm computes a single aggregate vector per predefined cluster, it cannot model simultaneous multi-directional branching (bifurcations) originating from a single population, as observed in the root HSC cluster. While piecewise linear approximation of branching manifolds is possible through finer sub-clustering, this introduces a trade-off. Fine sub-clustering reduces the number of cells per micro-cluster, diminishing the statistical power required for L-moment estimation and increasing susceptibility to sampling noise. Consequently, L-Trail requires graph-based clustering (e.g., Leiden) at an appropriate resolution; algorithms that impose isotropic boundaries (e.g., k -means) or over-clustering tend to truncate the manifold, potentially altering the geometric asymmetry[15].

3.5 Geometric Constraints and Conservative Design

The application of L-Trail to the Dentate Gyrus dataset, alongside observations in the Pancreas and Paul15 datasets, defines the geometric boundaries and safety mechanisms of the algorithm. The absence of estimated vectors in steady-state progenitor pools (e.g., Radial Glia-like) and small clusters (e.g., OL, Cck-Tox) demonstrates the function of the built-in permutation test. Rather than computing vectors from sparse or symmetric data, L-Trail suppresses output, preventing the generation of artifactual trajectories. Conversely, we observed backward flows in specific progenitor populations, such as the Neuroblast cluster, the Ngn3 low EP cluster, and the early undifferentiated populations in the Paul15 dataset.

We attribute these directional reversals to a geometric distinction between two transitional phases: the progressing state and the initiating state. Based on the mathematical definition ($v_d = -l_3^{(d)}$), L-Trail is designed for populations in a progressing state. These advancing clusters exhibit a directional topology characterized by a dense head of cells accumulating near the transition boundary and a sparse, trailing tail of delayed cells. In this configuration, negating the L-skewness aligns the vector toward the developmental endpoint. In contrast, early uncommitted populations represent initiating states. These clusters consist of progenitor pools where a subset of cells has begun to transition. In such distributions, the cellular density is highest at the originating state, and a sparse "comet tail" extends forward into the developmental space[16]. Consequently, the raw L-skewness ($l_3^{(d)}$) points forward, and the algorithm's negation forces the output vector to point backward. This highlights a limitation: while applicable to progressing populations accumulating toward a mature state, geometry-based inference inverts the biological timeline when applied to initiating progenitor pools.

3.6 Future Directions

While the current implementation of L-Trail utilizes L-skewness to evaluate directional asymmetry, the L-moment framework offers broader analytical applications. In classical statistics, the relationship between L-skewness and L-kurtosis is utilized to identify probability distributions. Applying this bivariate evaluation to single-cell data enables the quantitative characterization of cluster-specific distributions, which could enhance state estimation within continuous manifolds.

The robustness of L-moments to extreme values extends their application beyond trajectory inference. Integrating these metrics into an scRNA-seq preprocessing pipeline—specifically within dimensionality reduction and clustering algorithms—could provide a systematic approach to mitigate the effects of inherent sparsity and technical outliers.

L-Trail requires only the presence of a continuous data manifold. Consequently, this geometry-based framework is applicable beyond scRNA-seq to other single-cell modalities, including single-cell ATAC-seq (scATAC-seq) and continuous imaging features[17]. Furthermore, this approach is applicable to lower-dimensional, high-density modalities such as flow cytometry (FACS) and mass cytometry (CyTOF). In these datasets, the continuous asymmetric distributions are densely sampled, potentially facilitating geometric trajectory inference.

3.7 Conclusion

In conclusion, L-Trail is a geometry-dependent tool that extracts macroscopic transition trends from the asymmetric distribution of single-cell populations. While not intended to replace granular kinetic models, it serves as a transparent and splicing-independent complementary approach. The application of L-Trail relies on appropriate clustering resolution and geometry-preserving data transformations. Furthermore, recognizing its mathematical behavior—specifically its suitability for progressing states and its defined limitations in initiating states—is necessary for accurate interpretation. By accounting for these geometric principles, researchers can utilize L-Trail to infer macroscopic directional trends across diverse single-cell datasets.

4 Methods

4.1 Data Acquisition

All single-cell datasets analyzed in this study are publicly accessible and were obtained using the built-in dataset modules of the scanpy and scvelo Python libraries. Specifically, the Pancreas, Bone Marrow, and Dentate Gyrus datasets were acquired via the `scv.datasets.pancreas()`[18], `scv.datasets.bonemarrow()`[19], and `scv.datasets.dentategyrus()` functions[20], respectively. The Paul15 splicing-free dataset was retrieved using the `sc.datasets.paul15()` function[21].

4.2 L-moment Calculation

In single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) analysis, differentiating cells form continuous manifolds in a high-dimensional space, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) space. The distribution of a cell cluster along this manifold exhibits an asymmetric "comet tail," which indicates the direction of cellular transition. To capture this geometric asymmetry as an approach complementary to splicing kinetics, we developed L-Trail, a trajectory inference method based on L-moments[9]. Conventional central moments raise data to the third power, making them sensitive to outliers and technical noise in scRNA-seq data. In contrast, L-moments are constructed from linear combinations of Probability Weighted Moments (PWMs) based on order statistics[10], providing resistance to extreme values. For a given feature (e.g., a specific principal component d) with a sample of n cells, let the sorted values be $x_{(1)} \leq x_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq x_{(n)}$. The unbiased estimators of the first three PWMs (b_0, b_1, b_2) are defined as:

$$b_0 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n x_{(j)}$$

$$b_1 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=2}^n \frac{(j-1)}{(n-1)} x_{(j)}$$

$$b_2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=3}^n \frac{(j-1)(j-2)}{(n-1)(n-2)} x_{(j)}$$

Using these PWMs, the first three L-moments (l_1, l_2, l_3) are linearly computed as follows:

$$l_1 = b_0 \quad (\text{L-location})$$

$$l_2 = 2b_1 - b_0 \quad (\text{L-scale})$$

$$l_3 = 6b_2 - 6b_1 + b_0 \quad (\text{L-skewness})$$

In L-Trail, we calculate the L-moments for each dimension d in the high-dimensional space (e.g., top 30 PCs). To define the transition vector $\mathbf{V} = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_d]$ for a given cell cluster, we compute the L-skewness ratio $\tau_3^{(d)} = l_3^{(d)} / l_2^{(d)}$ to evaluate the asymmetry independent of scale. The directional component v_d is defined by reversing the sign and scaling back by the dispersion ($l_2^{(d)}$) so that the vector's magnitude reflects the spatial spread of the cells:

$$v_d = -\tau_3^{(d)} \times l_2^{(d)} = -l_3^{(d)}$$

The application of the negative sign is a required geometric transformation. During transition, a cell cluster exhibits a dense head of advanced cells and a sparse, trailing tail of delayed cells. Because statistical skewness points toward the tail, the forward direction of the developmental flow points in the opposite direction. By negating the L-skewness, L-Trail aligns the vector with the differentiation trajectory, while the magnitude reflects the directional bias.

4.3 Alternative Skewness Metric for Benchmarking

For benchmarking, we implemented a baseline trajectory inference method based on Pearson's second coefficient of skewness. Because standard moment-based skewness is susceptible to noise in sparse high-dimensional data, we selected this median-based approximation as a stable baseline. Similar to the L-skewness inversion, we reversed the standard formulation to ensure the vector points toward the transition endpoint rather than the sparse tail. In this approach, the directional vector for a cluster is defined by the scaled difference between the coordinate-wise median and mean:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{Pearson}} = 3 \times (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{median}} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{mean}})$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{median}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{mean}}$ are the median and mean vectors of the cluster in the high-dimensional space. We utilized this metric in comparative analyses to evaluate the geometric stability of L-Trail against a conventional statistical metric.

4.4 Statistical Significance via Permutation Test

In sparse single-cell datasets, random variations can produce geometric skewness. To test whether the computed L-Trail vector represents a biological transition rather than noise, we perform a non-parametric permutation test based on random sign-flipping[11]. Let $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be the coordinate vector of the i -th cell in a cluster of n cells. We center the data by subtracting the mean vector $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$, resulting in the centered coordinate \mathbf{x}'_i :

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{x}_i$$

$$\mathbf{x}'_i = \mathbf{x}_i - \bar{\mathbf{x}}$$

This centering sets up the null hypothesis that the data is symmetrically distributed around its centroid. To generate a null distribution, we multiply each cell's centered coordinate vector \mathbf{x}'_i by a random sign variable $s_i \in \{-1, 1\}$. The randomized coordinate \mathbf{x}^*_i is given by:

$$\mathbf{x}_i^* = s_i \cdot \mathbf{x}_i' \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, n$$

For each iteration (default $N = 100$), we calculate the L-Trail vector \mathbf{v}^* from the randomized data \mathbf{X}^* and record its Euclidean norm $m^* = \|\mathbf{v}^*\|_2$. Let $m_{\text{obs}} = \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{obs}}\|_2$ be the magnitude of the observed L-Trail vector computed from the original data \mathbf{X} . The empirical p -value is calculated as the proportion of randomizations that yielded a magnitude greater than or equal to the observed magnitude:

$$p = \frac{1 + \sum_{b=1}^N I(m_b^* \geq m_{\text{obs}})}{1 + N}$$

where $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function. Vectors with a p -value above a threshold (e.g., $p \geq 0.05$) are excluded from downstream analyses. We compute the vector norm across the entire d -dimensional space ($d = 30$) rather than a low-dimensional projection space. The accumulation of random variations across multiple dimensions inflates the baseline magnitude of the null distribution. Consequently, the observed magnitude (m_{obs}) must exceed this high-dimensional noise floor to achieve statistical significance, filtering out low-dimensional artifacts.

4.5 Visualization and Projection of Trajectories

Because L-Trail computes trajectory vectors based on linear combinations of Probability Weighted Moments, interpreting these vectors within linear dimensionality reduction spaces (e.g., PCA) avoids projection artifacts. However, to accommodate the use of non-linear embeddings like UMAP or t-SNE for visualization[22, 23], we implemented a manifold-aware k -nearest neighbors (k -NN) projection strategy. For a cell cluster, let \mathbf{c}_{high} be its centroid and \mathbf{v}_{high} be the computed L-Trail vector in the high-dimensional space. We define a theoretical future state \mathbf{f}_{high} by stepping along the directional vector:

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{high}} = \mathbf{c}_{\text{high}} + s \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\text{high}}$$

where s is an adjustable scaling factor. To map this trajectory onto a 2D space, we identify the k -nearest neighbors for the start point (\mathbf{c}_{high}) and the theoretical future point (\mathbf{f}_{high}) among the observed cells in the high-dimensional space. Assuming each observed cell is mapped to a 2D embedding coordinate \mathbf{y} , let $\mathbf{Y}_{\text{start}}$ and \mathbf{Y}_{end} be the sets of 2D coordinates corresponding to these k neighbor cells. The mapped 2D start point \mathbf{c}_{2D} and end point \mathbf{f}_{2D} are approximated as the spatial means of these local neighborhoods:

$$\mathbf{c}_{2D} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{Y}_{\text{start}}} \mathbf{y}$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{2D} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{Y}_{\text{end}}} \mathbf{y}$$

The trajectory is drawn from \mathbf{c}_{2D} to \mathbf{f}_{2D} . While this approach ensures that projected arrows adhere to the observed cell manifold, distances and directions in non-linear spaces are distorted; analytical interpretations should rely on the high-dimensional linear space.

4.6 Quantitative Evaluation of Local Trajectory Alignment

To evaluate the directional concordance between L-Trail and RNA velocity, we compute the cosine similarity between the L-Trail and reference vectors within local micro-environments randomly sampled across the high-dimensional manifold. Let \mathbf{X} be the high-dimensional representation of the dataset comprising N_{total} cells. We sample a subset of M anchor cells (e.g., $M = 1000$). For each

anchor cell i , we identify its local neighborhood \mathcal{N}_i consisting of its k -nearest neighbors using the Euclidean distance in \mathbf{X} . Within each local neighborhood \mathcal{N}_i , we compute the L-Trail directional vector $\mathbf{v}_{\text{LT}}^{(i)}$. We define the local reference vector $\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}^{(i)}$ as the mean RNA velocity vector of cells in \mathcal{N}_i :

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \mathbf{u}_j$$

where \mathbf{u}_j is the high-dimensional RNA velocity vector of cell j . To quantify the alignment at the i -th anchor, we calculate the cosine similarity $S_c^{(i)}$:

$$S_c^{(i)} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\text{LT}}^{(i)} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}^{(i)}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{LT}}^{(i)}\|_2 \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}^{(i)}\|_2}$$

The cosine similarity $S_c \in [-1, 1]$ measures the angular alignment: $S_c \approx 1$ indicates that the trajectories point in the same direction, $S_c \approx 0$ indicates orthogonality, and $S_c < 0$ indicates opposing directions. Evaluating S_c across anchor points generates a statistical distribution of vector alignments for each cell cluster.

4.7 Data Preprocessing and Dimensionality Reduction

For the Pancreas and Dentate Gyrus datasets, raw count matrices were processed using the scVelo and Scanpy pipelines. To ensure sufficient splicing information for subsequent RNA velocity estimation, genes with fewer than 20 shared counts across spliced and unspliced layers were excluded. Total counts per cell were normalized, followed by logarithmic ($\log_1 p$) transformation. The top 2,000 highly variable genes were selected. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed, and a k -nearest neighbors (k -NN) graph was constructed using the top 30 principal components ($d = 30$) and $k = 30$. Based on this neighborhood graph, first-order moments of splicing kinetics were computed for each cell.

For the splicing-free Paul15 dataset, the raw count matrix was initially preserved as a separate layer. Cells expressing fewer than 200 genes and genes expressed in fewer than 3 cells were excluded. Total counts per cell were then normalized to a target sum of 10,000. To evaluate trajectory inference independently of splicing kinetics, the dataset was processed through two parallel pipelines post-normalization: one pipeline utilized the standard $\log_1 p$ transformation, while the other utilized a square-root (sqrt) transformation. In both pipelines, the top 2,000 highly variable genes (HVGs) were identified using the `seurat_v3` flavor[24] based entirely on the unnormalized raw count layer. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed strictly on these 2,000 HVGs ($d = 30$), followed by k -nearest neighbors (k -NN) graph construction ($k = 30$, using the top 30 PCs), Leiden clustering, and UMAP embedding.

RNA Velocity Estimation For datasets containing spliced and unspliced transcript counts, RNA velocity was computed using the scVelo pipeline. The stochastic model was applied to the Pancreas dataset, while the dynamical model was applied to the Dentate Gyrus dataset. For the Bone Marrow dataset, the preprocessing and velocity estimation pipelines were specifically adjusted to account for complex splicing dynamics across distinct hematopoietic lineages. Gene filtering (`min_shared_counts=30`) and per-cell normalization were performed using scVelo preprocessing modules, followed by $\log_1 p$ transformation and the selection of the top 2,000 HVGs. The RNA velocity vector field was inferred using the dynamical model. To resolve multiple transcriptional regimes, the full splicing dynamics were recovered (`scv.tl.recover_dynamics`), differential kinetic testing was performed (`scv.tl.differential_kinetic_test`), and differential kinetics were explicitly integrated (`diff_kinetics=True`) into the final velocity calculation.

L-Trail directional vectors were computed within the high-dimensional PCA space using the top 30 principal components. Cell clusters containing fewer than 30 cells were excluded from the trajectory inference. To assess statistical significance, a permutation test based on random sign-flipping of centered coordinates was performed. While the algorithm defaults to 1,000 permutations, for the datasets analyzed in this study, the empirical p -value was calculated using 100 bootstrap iterations ($N = 100$), providing sufficient resolution to evaluate the $p < 0.05$ significance threshold while maintaining computational efficiency. Only directional vectors achieving statistical significance against the high-dimensional noise floor were retained for downstream analyses.

Low-Dimensional Projection of Trajectory Vectors To visualize the inferred high-dimensional vectors on two-dimensional embeddings (PCA or UMAP), the starting and future endpoints of each vector were mapped using a k -NN projection approach. A k -NN graph ($k = 30$) was constructed in the PCA space to identify the nearest neighbors of the vector coordinates, and the mean 2D coordinates of these neighbors were used to draw the projected vectors. For consistent visual comparison across plots, the lengths of the projected vectors were uniformly scaled by a factor of $s = 30$ for L-Trail vectors and $s = 5$ for Pearson's skewness vectors.

Quantitative Evaluation of Trajectory Alignment The directional concordance between the L-Trail and RNA velocity vector fields was quantitatively evaluated using a local k -NN sampling approach. A total of 1,000 anchor cells were randomly sampled (random seed = 34). Local micro-environments were defined using $k = 50$ nearest neighbors within the top 30 PCA dimensions. The cosine similarity was calculated between the local L-Trail directional vector and the mean RNA velocity vector within each defined micro-environment.

4.8 Software and Reproducibility

All computational analyses were performed using Python. The primary single-cell data processing, trajectory inference, and visualization were conducted using scanpy (v1.12.0) and scvelo (v0.3.4)[25, 3]. Additional core dependencies included anndata (v0.12.10)[26], numpy (v2.0.2), pandas (v2.3.3), scipy (v1.16.3), scikit-learn (v1.6.1), and leidenalg (v0.11.0)[15]. To guarantee the strict reproducibility of all stochastic processes—including highly variable gene selection, principal component analysis, k -NN graph construction, Leiden clustering, and UMAP dimensional reduction—a global random seed was fixed to 34 across all relevant computational modules (random, numpy.random, scanpy.settings.seed, and scvelo.settings.seed).

Data and Code Availability

References

- [1] Tallulah S Andrews and Martin Hemberg. Identifying cell populations with scrnaseq. *Molecular aspects of medicine*, 59:114–122, 2018.
- [2] Gioele La Manno, Ruslan Soldatov, Amit Zeisel, Emelie Braun, Hannah Hochgerner, Viktor Petukhov, Katja Lidschreiber, Maria E Kastrioti, Peter Lönnerberg, Alessandro Furlan, et al. Rna velocity of single cells. *Nature*, 560(7719):494–498, 2018.
- [3] Volker Bergen, Marius Lange, Stefan Peidli, F Alexander Wolf, and Fabian J Theis. Generalizing rna velocity to transient cell states through dynamical modeling. *Nature biotechnology*, 38(12):1408–1414, 2020.

- [4] Laleh Haghverdi, Maren Büttner, F Alexander Wolf, Florian Buettner, and Fabian J Theis. Diffusion pseudotime robustly reconstructs lineage branching. *Nature methods*, 13(10):845–848, 2016.
- [5] Cole Trapnell, Davide Cacchiarelli, Jonna Grimsby, Prapti Pokharel, Shuqiang Li, Michael Morse, Niall J Lennon, Kenneth J Livak, Tarjei S Mikkelsen, and John L Rinn. The dynamics and regulators of cell fate decisions are revealed by pseudotemporal ordering of single cells. *Nature biotechnology*, 32(4):381–386, 2014.
- [6] Gunsagar S Gulati, Shaheen S Sikandar, Daniel J Wesche, Anoop Manjunath, Anjan Bhadraraj, Mark J Berger, Francisco Ilagan, Angera H Kuo, Robert W Hsieh, Shang Cai, et al. Single-cell transcriptional diversity is a hallmark of developmental potential. *Science*, 367(6476):405–411, 2020.
- [7] Adam Gayoso, Philipp Weiler, Mohammad Lotfollahi, Dominik Klein, Justin Hong, Aaron Streets, Fabian J Theis, and Nir Yosef. Deep generative modeling of transcriptional dynamics for rna velocity analysis in single cells. *Nature methods*, 21(1):50–59, 2024.
- [8] Peter V Kharchenko. The triumphs and limitations of computational methods for scrna-seq. *Nature methods*, 18(7):723–732, 2021.
- [9] J. R. M. Hosking. L-moments: Analysis and estimation of distributions using linear combinations of order statistics. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)*, 52(1):105–124, 1990.
- [10] J Arthur Greenwood, J Maciunas Landwehr, Nicolas C Matalas, and James R Wallis. Probability weighted moments: definition and relation to parameters of several distributions expressible in inverse form. *Water resources research*, 15(5):1049–1054, 1979.
- [11] Anderson M Winkler, Gerard R Ridgway, Matthew A Webster, Stephen M Smith, and Thomas E Nichols. Permutation inference for the general linear model. *Neuroimage*, 92:381–397, 2014.
- [12] Chen Qiao and Yuanhua Huang. Representation learning of rna velocity reveals robust cell transitions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(49):e2105859118, 2021.
- [13] F William Townes, Stephanie C Hicks, Martin J Aryee, and Rafael A Irizarry. Feature selection and dimension reduction for single-cell rna-seq based on a multinomial model. *Genome biology*, 20(1):295, 2019.
- [14] Gennady Gorin, Meichen Fang, Tara Chari, and Lior Pachter. Rna velocity unraveled. *PLoS computational biology*, 18(9):e1010492, 2022.
- [15] Vincent A Traag, Ludo Waltman, and Nees Jan Van Eck. From louvain to leiden: guaranteeing well-connected communities. *Scientific reports*, 9(1):5233, 2019.
- [16] Mitra Mojtahedi, Alexander Skupin, Joseph Zhou, Ivan G Castaño, Rebecca YY Leong-Quong, Hannah Chang, Kalliopi Trachana, Alessandro Giuliani, and Sui Huang. Cell fate decision as high-dimensional critical state transition. *PLoS biology*, 14(12):e2000640, 2016.
- [17] Jason D Buenrostro, M Ryan Corces, Caleb A Lareau, Beijing Wu, Alicia N Schep, Martin J Aryee, Ravindra Majeti, Howard Y Chang, and William J Greenleaf. Integrated single-cell analysis maps the continuous regulatory landscape of human hematopoietic differentiation. *Cell*, 173(6):1535–1548, 2018.
- [18] Aimée Bastidas-Ponce, Sophie Tritschler, Leander Dony, Katharina Scheibner, Marta Tarquis-Medina, Ciro Salinno, Silvia Schirge, Ingo Burtscher, Anika Böttcher, Fabian J Theis, et al. Comprehensive single cell mrna profiling reveals a detailed roadmap for pancreatic endocrinogenesis. *Development*, 146(12):dev173849, 2019.

- [19] Manu Setty, Vaidotas Kisieliovas, Jacob Levine, Adam Gayoso, Linas Mazutis, and Dana Pe'Er. Characterization of cell fate probabilities in single-cell data with palantir. *Nature biotechnology*, 37(4):451–460, 2019.
- [20] Hannah Hochgerner, Amit Zeisel, Peter Lönnerberg, and Sten Linnarsson. Conserved properties of dentate gyrus neurogenesis across postnatal development revealed by single-cell rna sequencing. *Nature neuroscience*, 21(2):290–299, 2018.
- [21] Franziska Paul, Ya'ara Arkin, Amir Giladi, Diego Adhemar Jaitin, Ephraim Kenigsberg, Hadas Keren-Shaul, Deborah Winter, David Lara-Astiaso, Meital Gury, Assaf Weiner, et al. Transcriptional heterogeneity and lineage commitment in myeloid progenitors. *Cell*, 163(7):1663–1677, 2015.
- [22] Leland McInnes, John Healy, and James Melville. Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03426*, 2018.
- [23] Laurens Van der Maaten and Geoffrey Hinton. Visualizing data using t-sne. *Journal of machine learning research*, 9(11), 2008.
- [24] Tim Stuart, Andrew Butler, Paul Hoffman, Christoph Hafemeister, Efthymia Papalexi, William M Mauck, Yuhan Hao, Marlon Stoeckius, Peter Smibert, and Rahul Satija. Comprehensive integration of single-cell data. *cell*, 177(7):1888–1902, 2019.
- [25] F Alexander Wolf, Philipp Angerer, and Fabian J Theis. Scanpy: large-scale single-cell gene expression data analysis. *Genome biology*, 19(1):15, 2018.
- [26] Isaac Virshup, Sergei Rybakov, Fabian J Theis, Philipp Angerer, and F Alexander Wolf. ann-data: Annotated data. *BioRxiv*, pages 2021–12, 2021.

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Conceptual overview and geometric stability of L-Trail.

(A) Schematic representation of the L-Trail algorithm. Within a continuous manifold, cell populations in a progressing transitional state form an asymmetric distribution in a high-dimensional space. The dense head represents advanced cells accumulating along the axis of transition, while the sparse tail consists of delayed cells. The forward trajectory is estimated by calculating the negative L-skewness ($-l_3$) based on order statistics.

(B) Evaluation of vector stability in the presence of technical noise. A simulated 1D cell distribution with introduced extreme outliers (red crosses) is used to compare the directional vector calculated by L-skewness ($-l_3$, blue arrow) and a baseline metric based on Pearson's second coefficient of skewness (v_{Pearson} , red arrow). The plot demonstrates the stability of the L-moment-based estimation against extreme values compared to the central moment-based approximation.

Figure 2. Comparative evaluation of L-Trail and RNA velocity in the Pancreas dataset.

(A) PCA embeddings of the Pancreas dataset. (Left) Streamlines representing the inferred RNA velocity vector field (stochastic mode). (Right) Cluster-specific directional vectors computed by L-Trail (black arrows), mapped onto the shared PCA space via a k -NN-based projection. Only significant vectors (permutation test $p < 0.05$) are shown. For visual clarity, the L-Trail directional vectors projected onto the 2D space are uniformly scaled by an adjustable factor ($s = 30$).

(B) Total number of cells (n) for each annotated cluster.

(C) Quantitative evaluation of local trajectory alignments. Violin and box plots show the distribution of cosine similarities between L-Trail and RNA velocity vectors, calculated within local k -NN micro-environments centered on 1,000 randomly sampled anchor cells. Cell clusters are sorted in descending order of their median similarity scores (Med). The n value below each cluster indicates the number of sampled anchor cells, distinct from the total cell counts in (B). The horizontal dashed line at 0 indicates orthogonality.

(D) Spatial visualization of local trajectory alignments. Evaluated anchor cells are projected onto the PCA space and colored according to their cosine similarity scores, indicating regional directional concordance (red) and divergence (blue).

Note: Cluster annotations are superimposed directly onto the plots. For visualization purposes, the L-Trail directional vectors projected onto the 2D space are uniformly scaled by a factor of $s = 30$.

Figure 3. Comparative evaluation of L-Trail and RNA velocity in the Bone Marrow dataset.

(A) PCA embeddings of the Bone Marrow dataset. (Left) Streamlines representing the inferred RNA velocity vector field (dynamical mode). (Right) Cluster-specific directional vectors computed by L-Trail (black arrows), mapped onto the shared PCA space via a k -NN-based projection. Only significant vectors (permutation test $p < 0.05$) are shown. For visualization purposes, the plotted directional vector L-Trail is scaled by a factor of 30. Cluster labels are directly overlaid on the plots.

(B) Total number of cells (n) for each annotated cluster.

(C) Quantitative evaluation of local trajectory alignments. Violin and box plots show the distribution of cosine similarities between L-Trail and RNA velocity vectors, calculated within local k -NN micro-environments centered on 1,000 randomly sampled anchor cells. Cell clusters are sorted in descending order of their median similarity scores (Med). The n value below each cluster indicates the number of sampled anchor cells, distinct from the total cell counts in (B). The horizontal dashed line at 0 indicates orthogonality.

Note: Cluster annotations are superimposed directly onto the plots. For visualization purposes, the L-Trail directional vectors projected onto the 2D space are uniformly scaled by a factor of $s = 30$.

Figure 4. Evaluation of L-Trail on the splicing-free Paul15 dataset and comparison with Diffusion Pseudotime.

(A) Trajectory analysis of the Paul15 dataset using standard log1p normalization. (Left) Cluster-specific directional vectors computed by L-Trail (black arrows), mapped onto the PCA space. Only significant vectors (permutation test $p < 0.05$) are shown. (Right) The shared PCA space colored by Diffusion Pseudotime (DPT), computed with the “7MEP” cluster defined as the developmental root. For visualization purposes, the plotted directional vectors L-Trail and v_{Pearson} are scaled by factors of 30 and 5, respectively.

(B) Trajectory analysis of the same dataset using square-root (sqrt) normalization. (Left) L-Trail directional vectors. (Right) Corresponding DPT projection. Across both normalization strategies, the global directional trends inferred by L-Trail align directionally with the pseudotemporal gradient established by DPT.

Note: For visualization purposes, the plotted directional vectors L-Trail and v_{Pearson} are scaled by factors of 30 and 5, respectively.

Figure 5. Comparative evaluation of L-Trail and RNA velocity in the Dentate Gyrus dataset.

(A) PCA embeddings of the Dentate Gyrus dataset. (Left) Streamlines representing the inferred RNA velocity vector field (dynamical mode). (Right) Cluster-specific directional vectors computed by L-Trail (black arrows), mapped onto the shared PCA space via a k -NN-based projection. Only significant vectors (permutation test $p < 0.05$) are shown. For visualization purposes, the plotted directional vector L-Trail is scaled by a factor of 30. Cluster labels are directly overlaid on the plots.

(B) Total number of cells (n) for each annotated cluster.

(C) Quantitative evaluation of local trajectory alignments. Violin and box plots show the distribution of cosine similarities between L-Trail and RNA velocity vectors, calculated within local k -NN micro-environments centered on 1,000 randomly sampled anchor cells. Cell clusters are sorted in descending order of their median similarity scores (Med). The n value below each cluster indicates the number of sampled anchor cells, distinct from the total cell counts in (B). The horizontal dashed line at 0 indicates orthogonality.

Note: Cluster annotations are superimposed directly onto the plots. For visualization purposes, the L-Trail directional vectors projected onto the 2D space are uniformly scaled by a factor of $s = 30$.

Figure 1: Conceptual overview and geometric stability of L-Trail.

Figure 2: Comparative evaluation of L-Trail and RNA velocity in the Pancreas dataset.

Figure 3: Comparative evaluation of L-Trajectory and RNA velocity in the Bone Marrow dataset.

Figure 4: Evaluation of L-Trail on the splicing-free Paul15 dataset and comparison with Diffusion Pseudotime.

Figure 5: Comparative evaluation of L-Trail and RNA velocity in the Dentate Gyrus dataset.

Figure S1. Comparison of trajectory inference using scVelo, L-Trail, and Pearson’s skewness across PCA and UMAP embeddings.

(A, B) Trajectory inference results for the Pancreas dataset projected onto the (A) PCA and (B) UMAP spaces. In each panel, from left to right: streamlines representing the scVelo vector field (stochastic mode); cluster-specific directional vectors computed by L-Trail (black arrows; permutation test $p < 0.05$); and directional vectors computed using Pearson’s second coefficient of skewness (v_{Pearson}).

(C, D) Corresponding trajectory inference results for the Bone Marrow dataset projected onto the (C) PCA and (D) UMAP spaces. From left to right: scVelo vector field (dynamical mode), L-Trail directional vectors ($p < 0.05$), and v_{Pearson} directional vectors.

Note: For visual clarity, the L-Trail and v_{Pearson} directional vectors are uniformly scaled by factors of $s = 30$ and $s = 5$, respectively. Cluster labels are directly overlaid on the plots.

Figure S2. Comparison of trajectory inference using scVelo, L-Trail, and Pearson’s skewness across PCA and UMAP embeddings in the Dentate Gyrus dataset.

(A, B) Trajectory inference results for the Dentate Gyrus dataset projected onto the (A) PCA and (B) UMAP spaces. In each panel, from left to right: streamlines representing the scVelo vector field (dynamical mode); cluster-specific directional vectors computed by L-Trail (black arrows; permutation test $p < 0.05$); and directional vectors computed using Pearson’s second coefficient of skewness (v_{Pearson}).

Note: For visual clarity, the L-Trail and v_{Pearson} directional vectors are uniformly scaled by factors of $s = 30$ and $s = 5$, respectively. Cluster labels are directly overlaid on the plots.

Figure S3. Cell cluster annotations and distributions for the Paul15 dataset.

(A) PCA embeddings of the Paul15 dataset colored by annotated cell types. The plots illustrate the spatial distribution of cells processed with standard log1p normalization (left) and square-root (sqrt) normalization (right).

(B) Legend detailing the annotated cell clusters.

(C) Total number of cells (n) for each annotated cluster.

Note: This figure serves as the spatial reference for the trajectory analysis presented in Figure 4. Cluster labels are directly overlaid on the plots in (A).

Figure S4. Impact of Leiden clustering resolution on trajectory inference in the Pancreas dataset.

(A, B) Trajectory inference results for the Pancreas dataset projected onto the (A) UMAP and (B) PCA spaces across varying Leiden clustering resolutions (0.3, 0.5, and 1). In each panel, the top row displays cluster-specific directional vectors computed by L-Trail (black arrows; permutation test $p < 0.05$), and the bottom row displays directional vectors computed using Pearson’s second coefficient of skewness (v_{Pearson}). Note: For visual clarity, the L-Trail and v_{Pearson} directional vectors are uniformly scaled by factors of $s = 30$ and $s = 5$, respectively.

Figure S1: Comparison of trajectory inference using scVelo, L-Trail, and Pearson's skewness across PCA and UMAP embeddings.

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